

The Differential Recycle Reactor for Efficient Kinetic Measurements in Heterogeneously Catalyzed Gas-Liquid Reactions

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Abstract

Obtaining reliable kinetic data for heterogeneously catalyzed gas-liquid reactions under industrially relevant conditions is difficult because conventional laboratory reactors often provide limited control over hydrodynamics and yield little kinetic information per experiment. This work presents a differential recycle reactor (DRR) for rapid kinetic measurements in gas-liquid fixed-bed catalysis. The reactor enables controlled gas and liquid flow through the catalyst bed, operation at elevated temperatures and pressures, and time-resolved kinetic data from a single batch experiment. Two reactor designs were developed and evaluated based on bed structure, fluid distribution, and suitability for kinetic analysis. Model-based sensitivity studies identified operating windows in which the DRR approaches ideal batch-reactor behavior, enabling accurate kinetic evaluation with a simplified batch model. The predicted behavior was validated experimentally through an industrially relevant core hydrogenation. The results show that the DRR is a practical method for efficient macrokinetic measurements under realistic operating conditions and is suitable for routine kinetic studies and future coupling with online analytics.

Keywords

(1.) Hydrogenation (2.) Laboratory Reactor (3.) Multiphase Reaction Kinetics (4.) Macrokinetic (5.) Trickle Bed (6.) Experimental Efficiency (7.) Core Hydrogenation (8.) Differential Reactor

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1 Introduction

Heterogeneously catalyzed gas-liquid syntheses are foundational to numerous industrial processes. [1–5] Among the available technologies, fixed-bed reactors are the most prevalent. In these reactors, catalyst particles, such as spheres or pellets, are arranged in a stationary packed bed. [5] The phases of gas and liquid are known to flow co-currently through the bed, where the desired chemical reactions take place. [6, 7] Prominent industrial examples include hydrogenation reactions, such as the selective conversion of an aromatic core. [1, 8, 9] The design of reliable reactors, the assurance of operational safety, and the optimization of the process all depend critically on accurate kinetic data. [10, 11]

In principle, two primary strategies have been developed to model the influence of the kinetics of such reactions on the composition and temperature profiles of the different phases in the reactor. [12, 13] The first strategy considers all phases explicitly using a multiphase reactor model (called heterogeneous model). The second strategy is a pseudo-homogeneous model approach that does not consider mass and heat transfer between phases explicitly, instead using lumped parameters.

In the heterogeneous model approach, all the elementary steps that contribute to the overall conversion or formation of species in the different phases are considered. [14] These steps generally encompass mass transport from the gas to the liquid phase, transport from the liquid bulk to the catalyst surface, intraparticle diffusion, adsorption onto active sites, the surface reaction itself, and subsequent product desorption. Each of these subprocesses is then described by an individual model. [3–5] In this particular instance, the kinetic model is employed to describe the intrinsic reaction rate occurring on the catalyst surface. This model is referred to as the microkinetic model. [4, 10] The main advantage of this approach is its ability to predict the complex, non-linear relationship between the overall conversion rate and particular operating parameters, such as temperature, pressure and catalyst properties. [15–17]

However, the development of a robust, heterogeneous model necessitates a profound, fundamental understanding of each constituent subprocess. [3, 14] Moreover, given the limited predictive accuracy of theoretical models, they must be parameterized with extensive experimental data. [16] In an ideal scenario, this parameterization would necessitate the independent investigation of each subprocess, resulting in a substantial experimental workload. [10, 11] Consequently, the heterogeneous model approach is seldom employed

for routine industrial process development due to its complexity and high cost. [18–20] In industrial practice, the pseudo-homogenous model, when employed in conjunction with a macrokinetic approach, is frequently the preferred method for describing the kinetics of heterogeneously catalyzed gas-liquid reactions. [9, 12, 13, 15, 21–25]

The pseudo-homogenous model approach is distinct from the heterogeneous model approach in that it is based on the macrokinetic model, which describes the observed (or apparent) rate of reaction in dependence of observable bulk properties (temperature, composition, pressure, etc.). [2, 22] This approach is subject to limitations in its capacity to predict conversion rates of reactants and formation rates of products outside the experimental parameters utilized to parameterize the model. [26, 27] This phenomenon can be attributed to its inability to account for the non-linear interaction of all sub-processes. [17] Consequently, the utilization of a macrokinetic model for the description of an industrial synthesis necessitates the execution of an experimental investigation within a laboratory setting, ensuring the comparability of the conditions to those prevailing in industrial operation. [26, 28] Therefore, it is imperative that the catalyst is identical in terms of its shape, size, pore structure, and composition. The process conditions, including pressure, temperature, the composition of the gas and liquid phases, and the flow velocities of those phases, must be replicated in the laboratory in accordance with their observed or anticipated values for the industrial process. [18, 19, 29]

The application of the same catalyst in the laboratory as in the production scale is, in principle, a simple process. However, the aging effects that can be observed in the industrial process that is in operation for months or years are still difficult to reproduce in a laboratory setting. In order to reproduce industrial concentration profiles in the laboratory reactor the space velocity i.e., the flow rate of reactants per amount of catalyst must match that of the industrial fixed-bed reactor. In addition, comparable heat and mass transfer between the phases requires similar gas and liquid velocities within the packed bed under laboratory and industrial conditions. Taken together, these criteria imply, in principle, that the laboratory reactor should have the same catalyst-bed length as the industrial reactor. [30] In practice, this would lead to either a very long tubular laboratory reactor or a bundle of connected tubes.

However, this long laboratory reactor has several practical disadvantages. Firstly, filling the tubes with the catalyst is a time-consuming process. Secondly, in order to attain comparable temperature profiles in both reactors, it is imperative to minimize the heat losses in the laboratory tube reactor. This is due to the fact that the industrial reactor can often be regarded as adiabatic. [31, 32] Furthermore, due to the high surface-to-volume ratio in the laboratory reactor, even with a well-insulated reactor, significant heat losses are frequently observed, which are comparable to the enthalpy change caused by the reactions. Consequently, discrepancies in temperature profiles are inevitable between the laboratory and industrial reactors. [19] Thirdly, in order to obtain reliable kinetic information, it

is necessary to ensure that the laboratory reactor is in steady-state before commencing the sampling process. Furthermore, conventional offline sampling methodologies must be employed, as sophisticated inline process analysis techniques, such as magnetic resonance imaging utilized for fundamental research, are frequently not applicable in an industrial context. [33–35] Therefore, the spatial resolution of the measured concentration profiles is low (typically, a maximum of five to ten samples is collected along the length of the reactor). [36] As a result, the number of data points received per operational hour of the laboratory reactor is low, and the use of chemicals and the operational costs are high. It is evident that, despite the tubular reactor concept's inherent suitability for examining macrokinetics under industrial-relevant conditions, it is not particularly well suited for conducting rapid and systematic kinetic studies. [37–39]

The objective of this research is to engineer a laboratory reactor system, in conjunction with an integrated evaluation framework, that facilitates the expeditious and effective acquisition of macrokinetic data on heterogeneous catalysis in gas-liquid reaction systems. A thorough analysis has identified the differential recycle reactor (DRR) operating in batch mode to be the most suitable option for this purpose. In the DRR design, the fixed-bed reactor is composed of a tube that has been filled with a small amount of catalyst. Through this tube, the liquid reaction mixture and the gas phase are passed. Subsequently, the reaction mixture is introduced into a buffer vessel, and is then recycled back to the tubular reactor while the unreacted gas phase is purged. The occurrence of a reaction is confined to the reactor containing the catalyst while the majority of the liquid reaction mixture is situated in the buffer tank. Therefore, the temporal concentration change of the reaction mixture observed during a single batch experiment in the DRR reactor is analogous to the spatial concentration change found in the industrially fixed-bed reactor operated in steady-state. [2, 40] The design and operation of DRRs offer several advantages over the tubular reactor concept. [10, 41]

The proposed DRR configuration can easily be designed to function under harsh conditions, such as high temperatures and pressures, which are often required for industrial syntheses. [1] Furthermore, real industrial feedstocks and reaction mixtures (e.g., without solvents) with industrially used solid catalyst particles (e.g., spheres and pellets) can be applied. The proposed reactor configuration facilitates straightforward sampling at elevated rates, thereby enabling the acquisition of a substantial amount of kinetic information for each experimental batch run. This results in the generation of numerous data points regarding the temporal concentration profiles of the reacting species. As the samples are extracted from the buffer tank, the flow within the catalyst bed remains undisturbed.

In order to facilitate the reliable transfer of macrokinetic information from the laboratory to the production scale, it is essential that the hydrodynamic conditions and, by extension, the internal mass and heat transfer are comparable between scales. In practice, this necessitates the matching of the superficial velocities of both the gas and liquid phases

in the catalyst bed as well as the porosity of the catalyst bed. In the DRR, the superficial velocities can be directly adjusted and reliably reproduced through control of the volumetric flow rates through the packed bed. Conversely, stirred tanks equipped with baskets packed with catalyst control mixing indirectly via impeller speed. The actual flow through the catalyst bed cannot be controlled directly. [39, 42] Moreover, the flow rate through the catalyst bed in stirred tank reactors is difficult to predict, resulting in the actual value remaining unknown. This lack of knowledge complicates the scale-up process from stirred tank experiments. Therefore, the ability to directly control the superficial velocities in the DRR represents a significant advantage over the stirred tank reactor design, which utilizes a catalyst basket. The DRR concept facilitates the examination of the impact of mass transfer on macrokinetics in a series of controlled conditions.

Attaining congruence between the porosity of the catalyst bed in the DRR and that of the industrial reactor is a cumbersome task, as the porosity of the bed is significantly influenced by the geometry of the reactor. This factor is often disregarded in the design of laboratory reactors. [28, 43–45] In principle, achieving congruence between porosities of the catalyst bed in the DRR and the industrial reactor is only possible if the diameter ratio (i.e., the ratio of the diameter of the industrial reactor compared with the diameter of the particles) exceeds values of ten. [46, 47] This requirement of the diameter ratio results in a catalyst bed that is both very wide and short, resembling a thin slice. However, the configuration of the catalyst bed necessitates elevated flow rates of both gas and liquid phases through the bed to attain superficial velocities analogous to those observed in industrial-scale settings. It is evident that the resulting volume flow rates rapidly exceed the capacity of standard laboratory pumps and gas supplies. Consequently, an alternative design option was evaluated in this study. In this design, the diameter of the tube reactor is selected to be marginally larger than the diameter of the catalyst particle, thereby achieving a diameter ratio that approaches one. [48] The literature and the findings of our own investigations indicate that the porosity of the bed is approximately equivalent to the porosity observed in industrial-scale reactors with significantly larger diameter ratios. [49–52] Two design options for the catalyst beds were developed and tested in this study: one with a small diameter and large height, and the other with a large diameter and short bed height. A comprehensive discussion of the advantages and shortcomings of both designs is presented.

Additionally, the bed of both reactor designs must be meticulously packed to avert cavities, channeling, and dead zones. Consequently, experimental and computational investigations, incorporating CFD simulations and Computer Tomographic (CT) scans, were conducted in this work to optimize the reactor geometry including the in- and outlet and the packing procedure. The objective of this study was to ensure an homogeneous porosity of the bed and a uniform fluid flow through the catalyst bed of the DRR.

Another requirement on the kinetic measurements is that the evaluation of the experi-

mental data must be simple, i.e., it must be straightforward to derive kinetic information from the measurements. The aforementioned condition necessitates that the component balance of the reactants in the buffer vessel of the DRR can be described with sufficient accuracy by a simple reactor model. In this context, the term "simple" is used to denote a model with a minimal number of parameters that can be solved robustly with low numerical effort and high accuracy. These properties are essential for the reactor model, when employed in conjunction with the kinetic model, to facilitate the reliable estimation of kinetic parameters from substantial data sets, thus circumventing the necessity of utilizing specialized or computationally intensive numerical solvers. [15, 22] The aforementioned condition is theoretically attained when the conversion per single pass through the catalyst bed approaches zero, i.e., when the conversion is differential. [2, 53] In this instance, the component balance of the reactants in the buffer vessel can be described with a simple, ideally mixed batch reactor model. [54] Nevertheless, achieving differential conversion over the catalyst bed in the operational setting of a laboratory is challenging. This assertion is particularly relevant in the context of the long and small design option of the catalyst bed. In principle, a more complex reactor model is required in this case to account for the axial conversion profile over the catalyst bed. [55] The question thus arises as to whether there is a compelling rationale for the utilization of this intricate model, or if adopting a more simplistic approach, such as assuming differential conversion over the catalyst bed and employing the batch reactor model to describe the temporal variation in the composition of the buffer tank, would suffice. [56] In order to respond to this inquiry, a simulation-based error analysis was conducted in the present study. These results serve as a reference point for the selection of design and operating parameters.

Finally, the kinetics of heterogeneous-catalyzed core hydrogenation were investigated using the two design options for the catalyst bed. The results demonstrate the efficacy of the developed DRR setup in investigating kinetics under industrially relevant conditions. The design is characterized by its notable flexibility, which enables the adaptation of experimental conditions and procedures to the specific requirements of the chemical synthesis. The kinetic information obtained can be utilized directly for scale-up to industrial scale. Consequently, the DRR emerges as a pivotal instrument for the reliable scale-up, design, and optimization of heterogeneous-catalyzed gas-liquid reactions and the related reactors.

2 Design of the DRR

2.1 Concept and Design Criteria

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the DRR concept.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of a DRR for carrying out heterogeneously catalyzed solid-liquid-gas reactions. The liquid phase is completely recirculated. Reactant gas is continuously fed into the reactor, off-gas is discharged from the buffer tank.

The stirred buffer tank holds most of the liquid reaction mixture, while a circulation pump drives the flow of it through the fixed bed at adjustable flow rates. Reactant gas is continuously fed to the reactor and off-gas is purged from the tank. A major advantage of the DRR concept is eliminating stirrer-related issues common in conventional batch reactors (e.g. catalyst abrasion, undefined fluid dynamic conditions in catalyst baskets) when studying heterogeneously catalyzed reactions as mixing in the DRR is ensured by the circulation flow. Superficial velocities of the gas and liquid phase and therefore fluid flow characteristics can be adjusted to match industrial conditions. As previously discussed, if the conversion of the reactants per single pass through the catalyst bed is maintained at a low level (i.e., differential conversion occurs), the temporal change in the composition of the liquid phase in the buffer tank can be described by a simple ideally mixed batch reactor

model. In addition, a single sample point is sufficient to achieve the desired outcome. The necessity of measuring the composition differences before and after the catalyst bed, as is required for an intergal reactor concept, is thus eliminated. [10]

The design of the DRR follows several key requirements to balance practicality and scientific accuracy.

Requirement I – Design of the catalyst bed: The catalyst mass should be as small as possible to achieve differential conversion over the catalyst bed, while ensuring cost-effectiveness and material availability. At the same time, it must be sufficiently large to provide a statistically representative sample of particles. Typically, a sample comprising more than 100 particles is considered adequate for this purpose. Furthermore, as discussed in Section 1 the geometry of the catalyst bed must be designed to achieve a porosity that is comparable to that of the industrial reactor.

Requirement II – Design of the liquid buffer vessel: The initial liquid volume in the buffer tank must exceed the total sample volume required for frequent discrete sampling by a substantial margin. If this condition is not met, the ratio of reactant mass to catalyst mass, which is an important parameter for the kinetics, undergoes substantial variation during the course of the kinetic experiment. Conversely, a high ratio of reactant mass to catalyst mass can prolong the duration of experiments, as it takes a significant amount of time to reach high conversions of reactants. It is generally regarded as best practice that a DRR experiment should be completed within one working day.

In principle, the buffer tank or the circulation pipes offer excellent opportunities to install inline or online process analysis techniques, such as infra-red (IR), Raman, or Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. [33, 57–62] This approach eliminates the need for sampling and ensures the maintenance of a constant ratio of reactant to catalyst mass throughout the experiment. We demonstrated the potential of online process analysis for studying a heterogeneously catalyzed hydrogenation reaction in a stirred tank reactor using a benchtop NMR spectrometer. [63] The application of online process analysis in conjunction with the DRR concept will be presented in future work. This was not included in the scope of the present study.

Requirement III – Design of the liquid and gas streams: The superficial velocities of both the gas and liquid phases must be selected to match industrial process conditions of the studied system, with superficial velocities in the ranges of 5...20 m/h for the gas and 50...200 m/h for the liquid phase.

2.2 Design of the fixed-bed reactor

In order to ensure that bed porosity in the DRR is similar to that found in industrial fixed bed reactors (see Requirement I in Section 2.2), the bed porosity was measured in different tubular reactors with varying diameter. The results for a packing of spherical particles in a tube with a circular cross section are depicted in Figure 2 as function of the ratio of reactor diameter to particle diameter (in the following called reactor-to-particle diameter ratio). Hydrogenation experiments were conducted accordingly with spherical catalyst particles.

Figure 2: The bed porosity as function of the ratio of reactor diameter to particle diameter shown on logarithmic scale. Symbols: experimental results of this work using spherical particles (diameter: 4 mm). Solid line: Prediction using model of Cheng [50]. Dashed line: Predicted bulk bed porosity calculated for densest sphere packing.

As demonstrated in Figure 2, the bed porosity exhibits a high degree of sensitivity to the reactor-to-particle diameter ratio. In industrial fixed beds, this diameter ratio is typically in excess of ten, with a substantial margin, such that its value is equivalent to that of the bulk bed porosity. [46, 47] Especially for values of reactor-to-particle diameter ratio in the range of 1.5 to 4.0 the bed porosity deviates strongly from the bulk bed porosity expected for industrial scale reactors. Figure 3 depicts the computer tomographic image

of a catalyst bed filled with cylindrical extrudates that exhibits a unfavourable reactor-to-particle diameter ratio.

Figure 3: Computer tomographic scan of a packed bed reactor with catalyst bed (white cylinders). In the lower region of the image, dark hollow cavities are visible, resulting from ordered particle packing due to unfavorable geometry ratios. These channels impair homogeneous flow and catalytic efficiency. The CT scan was performed using a TomoScope L (Werth Messtechnik GmbH) with a voxel size of $49.6 \mu\text{m}$, 100 kV, 210 μA , an integration time of 334 ms, 1000 projections, a 1 mm aluminum filter, and an average of 5 scans per projection.

The image shows clearly the formation of voids and channels in the catalyst bed. It is obvious that these strong spacial variation of the bed porosity negatively influence fluid dynamics in the catalyst bed so that it deviates from the fluid dynamics in an industrial catalyst bed. It is important to note that in kinetic studies reported in the literature the critical aspect of designing a fixed-bed reactor with defined bed porosity is frequently overlooked. Conversely, due to their accessibility and straightforward configuration, reactor tubes with a reactor-to-particle diameter ratio of approximately two are frequently selected. [43–45] However, as demonstrated in this investigation, their use may not result in fluid dynamic conditions within the fixed bed that are conducive to scale-up.

As shown in Figure 2, the results indicate that two cases for the reactor diameters can be selected to guarantee comparable bed porosity in the laboratory reactor to that of an industrial reactor, namely, a wide reactor with reactor-to-particle diameter larger than 8

and a thin reactor with a diameter ratio of approximately 1.2 (see Figure 2). The latter reactor design necessitates the construction of a tube with a diameter that is only slightly wider than the catalyst particles. Although selecting the correct reactor-to-particle diameter ratio is necessary for achieving the proper bed porosity, it does not guarantee good flow through the bed. For the thin and long reactor, packing porosity is highly sensitive to catalyst diameter for a given reactor diameter making classification of the catalyst essential. However, when a proper procedure is followed a well defined packing with a defined porosity can be achieved, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Computer tomographic scan of a section of the thin reactor used in this study, packed with spherical particles. Channelling or maldistribution can be ruled out when considering the homogeneous random distribution of the particles. The CT scan was performed using a TomoScope L (Werth Messtechnik GmbH) with a voxel size of 49.6 μm , 240 kV, 146 μA , an integration time of 500 ms, 1600 projections, and a 1 mm aluminum filter.

Consequently, individual particles are arranged in a layered configuration, with each particle positioned on top of another. In order to achieve the requisite minimum amount of catalyst in the thin tube, it is essential that the tube and catalyst bed be of a specific length. In contrast the length of the catalyst bed of the wide reactor is short as both designs must contain the same amount of catalyst. The resulting dimensions and the operational parameters for both design options are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of design and the operational parameters for the two reactor options: I) wide/short and II) thin/long reactor. Only average values are given regarding confidential agreements.

Parameter	Wide/short reactor	Thin/long reactor	Unit
Diameter	40	6	mm
Bed height	14.7	653.3	mm
Catalyst mass	12.6	12.6	g
Max. liquid mass flow	58.0	2.7	kg h ⁻¹
Max. hydrogen gas consumption	890.1	63.4	Nm ³ h ⁻¹
Heat duty preheater	2.52	0.12	kW

The resulting reactor geometry is characterized by the ratio of reactor diameter d to reactor length l as dimensionless ratio δ :

$$\delta = \frac{d}{l} \quad (1)$$

Due to its large cross-sectional area, the wide reactor design requires large volume flow rates of gas and liquid phase to achieve the required superficial velocities in the catalyst bed (Requirement II), see Table 1. Practical limitations of gas supply and liquid pumping capacity in a laboratory environment quickly become apparent as well as the heat duty required for preheating the liquid phase.

In the wide reactor, bed porosity is less dependent on the filling procedure than in the thin and long reactor. This facilitates a substantial reduction in the time required for filling. However, the large cross-sectional area of the wide reactor makes it more difficult to achieve an even distribution of gas and liquid phase over the inlet of the catalyst bed and avoid maldistribution and channeling. For this reason, the inlet and outlet designs were expanded to include a relatively large freeboard area, in order to avoid changes in cross-section in proximity to the catalyst packing. Additionally, a bed of inert particles with a size and shape similar to the catalyst particles and a height of at least 20 mm was packed before and after the catalyst bed.

CFD simulations of single-phase liquid flow through sphere packings were performed to estimate the flow uniformity inside the wide/short reactor concept using a proprietary numerical workflow. The CAD geometry of the reactor was used as the input geometry for a proprietary automated packing generator tool comparable to approaches described in the literature. [49] This tool simulates the process of filling a given external geometry with particles and has been applied to packings with spherical particles comparable to the catalyst used in experiments. In this way, any influence of asymmetric connections on the

fluid flow, such as maldistribution within the packed bed, could be ruled out, and it was confirmed that the inert layer thickness required to achieve a uniform flow distribution was sufficient.

Figure 5 shows the results of the CFD simulation for the selected design, which validates a uniform fluid distribution.

Figure 5: Flow simulation of the wide/short reactor concept packed with spheres in single-phase downward flow configuration at a normalized superficial liquid velocity of $\bar{u} = 100$. The left picture displays the reactor overview with periphery. Right picture shows the cross-section of the packed bed. Colors represent normalized local fluid velocity: blue: 100, green: 200, red: >300 .

From a practical standpoint, the thin reactor offers significant advantages over the wide reactor, making its use highly advantageous in most cases. Reactors of this design were found to be cheaper to manufacture, as they consist of straightforward tubes, and can be operated with small circulation flows, so that standard laboratory pumps and heaters can be used. In contrast, manufacturing of the wide reactor design so that it is suitable for operations under high pressures and temperatures is not simple as it requires individual engineering. The main drawback of the thin and long reactor design, however, is that operation under strictly differential conversion conditions can, in principle, no longer be guaranteed. Whether and to what extent this deviation is critical is the central question addressed in the present work. Specifically, we seek to quantify the error in the kinetic data obtained when, instead of the relatively ideal but experimentally demanding wide/short reactor, a less ideal yet much simpler thin/long reactor design is employed.

2.3 Design of the buffer tank and periphery

With 270 ml the phase separator (i.e., buffer tank) was sized as large as necessary to enable representative sampling but as small as possible limiting equipment cost and holdup of chemicals (Requirement II). The buffer tank size was therefore directly linked to the used catalyst mass influencing the duration of the experiment and the maximum sample mass. Mild agitation is applied to promote uniform liquid composition while facilitating efficient gas separation. The design target is a well-mixed liquid phase with minimal spatial concentration gradients. Usually, a liquid hold-up of 100-200 ml was seen as sufficient for the experiments. Finally, the layout favored short piping runs to reduce pressure drop and dead volume.

The design of the auxiliary systems was guided by several practical constraints crucial for reliable operation. Because of the short residence time in the reactor, a dedicated preheater upstream of the reactor was required in addition to the reactor heating jacket to ensure isothermal reaction conditions. A coiled heat exchanger with a heat transfer surface of 0.06 m² heated by thermal oil was selected to achieve the necessary heat duty. The circulation pump had to handle the necessary pressure and temperature ranges and providing chemical resistance which was fulfilled by a high-performance gear pump. When operating at elevated flow rates, thermal losses of the recycle loop become significant to limit the required heat duty of the preheater. This was addressed by insulating the recycle loop including piping, pump, and phase separator. At the same time operating conditions and heat removal were controlled to prevent elevated temperatures that would increase vapor pressure and unintended stripping of liquid phase.

3 Simulative and Experimental Methods

3.1 Simulative Study on Deviation from Differential Conversion

3.1.1 Goal of the Study

This simulative pre-study aims to clarify the conditions under which the DRR can be validly treated as an ideally mixed batch reactor for kinetic evaluation. While the DRR is designed for differential conversion per pass, practical limitations (e.g., geometry, hydrodynamics, high reaction rates, see Chapter 2) inevitably result in finite conversions and axial concentration gradients within the catalyst bed. This is especially the case for the thin and long reactor design, in which significant axial concentration gradients can be expected.

The following procedure was applied to assess the error that arises when the simplified batch model is used to evaluate the experimental data:

1. A dynamic model of the entire DRR setup was developed using a compartment approach to account for the different parts of the setup, including the catalyst bed, the buffer tank, the pump, and the piping. The rate of reaction in the catalyst bed was described by a simple pseudo-homogeneous kinetic model.
2. The developed model was used to simulate the temporal concentration profiles of the reactants in the buffer tank. These simulations were performed for a given diameter-to-height ratio of the catalyst bed and superficial velocity of the liquid phase. The obtained data are considered *synthetic experimental data* generated by the rigorous DRR model.
3. In the subsequent step, the rate constant of the kinetic model was assumed to be unknown, and the synthetic experimental data was used to estimate this kinetic parameter. In contrast to the generation of synthetic data, the estimation was performed using a batch model. This model assumes an infinitesimally high recycling rate, corresponding to differential conversion over the catalyst bed.

3.1.2 Reactor Model

Figure 6 shows the compartmentalization of the DRR setup as tank-in-series model using continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTRs).

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the compartment model used to describe the DRR both in preliminary simulations and in experimental data evaluation. The setup is assumed to consist of a tank, a pump, the reactor and two pipes connecting the components. Every brown square represents a CSTR used to set up the compartment model. Discrete Apparatus are marked in grey ($K = 5$).

Each individual compartment is described as a non-steady-state CSTR. Accordingly each device K (representing the reactor, pipes, tank, or pump) is discretized into N_{CSTR}^K CSTRs with an individual liquid volume of V_l^K . The reactor bed is represented in the model by $m = 2$ parallel CSTR cascades in order to account for radial flow maldistribution (e.g., wall effects). Each of these cascades consists of n CSTRs arranged in a series. The total reactor volume, V^{FBR} , is therefore distributed among these two sections (V_m^{FBR}), where the parameter γ defines the ratio of the superficial fluid velocity u_{wall} in section $m = 1$ representing the annular area at the reactor wall and u_{core} in $m = 2$, which represents the central main part of the catalyst bed.

$$\gamma = \frac{u_{\text{wall}}}{u_{\text{core}}} \quad (2)$$

As a pseudo-homogeneous approach with regard to the liquid phase is used, the liquid

holdup of the FBR is reduced to the effective liquid Volume $V_{\text{eff}}^{\text{FBR}}$ according to the porosity of the catalyst bed as in Equation (3).

$$V_{\text{eff}}^{\text{FBR}} = \epsilon_{\text{cat}} \cdot V^{\text{FBR}} = \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{FBR}}} \epsilon_{\text{cat}} \cdot V_m^{\text{FBR}} \quad (3)$$

In order to match experimental conditions the total reaction volume $V(t)$ in the simulations is adjusted step-wise after each sampling point at sampling time t :

$$V_{\text{tot}}(t) = V_{\text{tot},t=0} - \sum_{x=1}^{n_{\text{samples}}(t)} V_{\text{sample},x}(t) \quad (4)$$

The general model equation is obtained by indexing the variables leading to Equation (5).

$$\frac{dc_i}{dt} = \frac{N_{\text{CSTR}}^K}{V_l} \cdot \dot{V}^K \cdot (c_i^{\text{in}} - c_i^{\text{out}}) - \frac{m_{\text{cat},l}}{N_{\text{CSTR}}^K} \cdot \sum \nu_{i,j} \cdot r_j \quad (5)$$

$$i = 1, \dots, k_{\text{components}}$$

$$j = 1, \dots, k_{\text{reactions}}$$

$$K = \{\text{FBR}, \text{Pipe}_1, \text{Tank}, \text{Pump}, \text{Pipe}_2\}$$

$$l = \begin{cases} n & K = \text{FBR} \\ v & K = \text{Pipe}_1 \\ 1 & K = \text{Tank} \\ 1 & K = \text{Pump} \\ w & K = \text{Pipe}_2 \end{cases}$$

$$m = 1, \dots, N_{\text{FBR}}$$

$$n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{CSTR},m}^{\text{FBR}}$$

$$v = 1, \dots, N_{\text{CSTR}}^{\text{pipe}_1}$$

$$w = 1, \dots, N_{\text{CSTR}}^{\text{pipe}_2}$$

$$V_l^K = \text{Volume of } l^{\text{th}} \text{ CSTR}$$

$$\dot{V} = \text{Volumetric recycle flow rate}$$

Only in the STRs representing the fixed-bed reactor, marked with ‘‘FBR’’ in Figure 6, does reaction take place. Piping is modelled in the same way as the FBR, with $m_{\text{cat}} = 0$ and hence no reaction term occurs. It therefore only provides a time-delaying element.

$$\frac{dc_i^{\text{pipe}_1}}{dt} = \frac{N^{\text{pipe}_1}}{V_w} \cdot \dot{V} \cdot (c_{i,w}^{\text{in}} - c_{i,w}^{\text{out}}) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dc_i^{\text{pipe}_2}}{dt} = \frac{N^{\text{pipe}_2}}{V_v} \cdot \dot{V} \cdot (c_{i,v}^{\text{in}} - c_{i,v}^{\text{out}}) \quad (7)$$

The buffer tank and pump represent physically discrete units and are therefore modeled as single CSTRs ($N_{\text{CSTR}}^{\text{pump}} = N_{\text{CSTR}}^{\text{tank}} = 1$) without reaction terms. Consequently, only mixing and dilution occur.

$$\frac{dc_i^{\text{tank}}}{dt} = \frac{1}{V^{\text{tank}}} \cdot \dot{V} \cdot (c_i^{\text{in}} - c_i^{\text{out}}) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dc_i^{\text{pump}}}{dt} = \frac{1}{V^{\text{pump}}} \cdot \dot{V} \cdot (c_i^{\text{in}} - c_i^{\text{out}}) \quad (9)$$

Chemical reaction is assumed to be first order with a rate of reaction r_j in respect to the catalyst mass m_{cat} present in each model compartment.

$$\frac{dc_i^{\text{FBR}}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{V}}{V_l^{\text{FBR}}} \cdot (c_i^{\text{in}} - c_i^{\text{out}}) + \frac{m_{\text{cat},l}}{V_l^{\text{FBR}}} \cdot \sum_j \nu_{i,j} r_j \quad (10)$$

A useful contrast is provided by a batch model, where the total liquid volume at given experimental time t and total catalyst mass are the same as in the compartment model.

$$\frac{dc_i}{dt} = -\frac{1}{V_{\text{tot}}(t)} \cdot m_{\text{cat}} \cdot r_i \quad (11)$$

Therefore, for infinitesimally small differential conversions in the FBR, the concentration profiles of both models should be identical. The presented compartment model and batch model are used both in purely simulation-based preliminary studies as well as in the subsequent evaluation of experimental data. This common kinetic framework allows simulated and experimental results to be compared directly, while the increasing model complexity primarily accounts for deviations of the specific laboratory reactor setup from the ideal DRR.

3.1.3 Model Implementation and Parameter Estimation

The parameters of the kinetic model are estimated by least-squares fitting. Estimates for the kinetic parameters were obtained by fitting the model to experimental data. The model predictions were performed using both the batch reactor model and the compartment-based DRR model. The fitting procedure involved minimizing the weighted sum of squared errors between experimental and predicted values of the target variable

c_i , as defined in Equation (12).

$$\begin{aligned}
 k &= \arg \min \sum_{x=1}^{n_{\text{sample}}} \sum_{i=1}^{k_{\text{comp}}} (c_{i,l}^{\text{obs}} - c_i^{\text{model}}(k, m_{\text{cat}}, V_{\text{tot}}))^2 \\
 i &= \{1 \text{ for } 1^{\text{st}} \text{ order reaction}\} \\
 x &= 1, \dots, n_{\text{sample}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Unlike standard approaches where the initial concentration is fixed based on gravimetric preparation, in this study, $c_{i,0}$ was derived solely from the first analytical sample at $t = 0$. Since this initial measurement is subject to the same analytical uncertainty as all subsequent data points, $c_{i,0}$ was not fixed but treated as a free fitting parameter. This approach avoids biasing the kinetic model towards an experimental value that carries its own measurement error. Experimental time was normalized such that t_0 corresponds to the time of the first sample, defining the start of the kinetic analysis. All data points were equally weighted during parameter estimation and no additional weighting factors were applied.

To improve the numerical stability of the optimization procedure and accelerate convergence, the kinetic parameters at each investigated temperature were transformed according to Equation (13). First, the kinetic parameters at each temperature were fitted separately. Second, the activation energy was determined using an Arrhenius plot with a reference temperature. Thus, a comprehensive, temperature-dependent kinetic parameter in the form of Equation (13) was obtained.

$$k = k_{T_{\text{ref}}} \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{E_a}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} \right) \right] \tag{13}$$

The global minimization problem was solved in Julia (version 1.8). In addition to the solver described in Section 3.1.3 the `LsqFit` package and the `DifferentialEquations` ODE solver with a standard `Tsit5` solver were applied. For each individual experimental run, the `LsqFit` package was applied to both a simple batch model and the more sophisticated compartment model, resulting in values for the individual rate constant. These values were then evaluated to determine the activation energy E_a .

To quantify the error introduced by using the simple batch model, the similarity number κ is defined as the ratio of the kinetic parameter estimated with the batch model to the true kinetic parameter used to generate synthetic experimental data.

$$\kappa = \frac{k_{\text{fit}}^*}{k} \tag{14}$$

To determine κ , a transient DRR experiment is simulated using the compartment model described above with a known intrinsic rate constant k . This yields a synthetic dataset

representing realistic laboratory sampling, as illustrated by the black circles in Figure 7. Subsequently, these synthetic data are fitted using the simple ideally mixed batch model to obtain an apparent rate constant k_{fit}^* . Figure 7 shows an example of the described procedure.

Figure 7: An exemplary comparison of synthetic experimental data of the concentration profiles using the DRR compartment model (symbols) and the fitted concentration profiles using the ideally mixed batch reactor model (blue line). In addition, the concentration profiles predicted with the ideally mixed batch reactor model using the same rate constant as for the calculation of the synthetic data is shown (red line).

In addition, Figure 7 shows also the concentration profile predicted with the batch reactor model when the same kinetic parameter is used as in the rigorous DRR model. The implications of the similarity factor κ regarding the model's behavior can be categorized as follows:

$\kappa < 1$: The DRR model achieves conversion slower than an ideally mixed batch reactor. Consequently, kinetic parameters derived under the batch assumption underestimate the true reaction rate. This represents the typical case for finite, realistic operating parameters.

$\kappa = 1$: The DRR behaves identically to an ideally mixed batch reactor. Kinetic parameters can be exactly determined using the batch model.

$\kappa > 1$: The DRR reaches conversion faster than an ideally mixed batch reactor, leading

to an overestimation of kinetics. This case is theoretically unlikely, as the ideally mixed batch reactor typically represents the limiting performance case.

For the purposes of this study, a similarity of $\kappa \geq 0.90$ (i.e., a deviation of less than 10%) is considered sufficient to meet the data quality requirements of industrial research environments.

The model for the DRR was set up according to Figure 6 with the catalyst mass being distributed evenly across the n CSTRs in the FBR based on the volume fraction. Initial reactant concentration $c_{A,0} = 10 \cdot 10^3$ is uniformly distributed throughout the DRR. The concentration in the model simulation is related to the volume V_{tot} of the total liquid reaction mass in the DRR.

The described simulation approach was used to perform a sensitivity analysis of the DRR model, systematically investigating the influence of key design and operating parameters on the similarity factor κ . Key parameters investigated include the superficial fluid velocity u (range: 5...100 m h⁻¹), the reactor geometry defined by the diameter-to-length ratio δ (range: 0.001...0.3 m m⁻¹), and the reaction kinetics represented by the rate constant k (range: 10⁻⁶...10⁻⁴ m³ kg⁻¹ s⁻¹).

To explicitly investigate the influence of wall channeling effects on the obtained kinetic parameters, the catalyst bed in the DRR compartment model was divided into two coaxial zones ($m = 2$) representing the core and wall flow regions, assuming complete segregation between the two. For consistency, the total reactor volume V^{FBR} and length l^{FBR} were kept constant across all simulations. The model assumes a core region covering 90 % of the cross-sectional area and a wall region covering 10 %, with catalyst mass distributed proportionally to the volume. The intensity of the wall flow is controlled via the flow split parameter γ (see Equation (2)). A range of $\gamma = 0$ to 9 was selected to evaluate scenarios of both reduced ($\gamma < 1$) and enhanced ($\gamma > 1$) wall flow relative to the nominal distribution ($\gamma = 1$). For evaluation of experimental data, the model was adapted to the actual laboratory setup.

3.2 Kinetic Investigations

3.2.1 Chemical System

The experimental test reaction system involves the selective hydrogenation of an aromatic ring (core hydrogenation). The highly exothermic reaction places special demands on the laboratory reactor. Due to confidentiality requirements, the exact molecular structure of the substrate cannot be disclosed. Instead, Figure 8 illustrates the generic reaction

scheme, representing the selective hydrogenation of a functional group on an aromatic core, which serves as the representative test system for this study.

Figure 8: Heterogeneously catalyzed selective hydrogenation of an aromatic ring in a complex organic molecule as test system. Only the functional groups relevant to the reaction are represented here.

Side products resulting from over-hydrogenation are not considered in the kinetic analysis, as the study focuses exclusively on the desired hydrogenation pathway. The reaction is conducted with a 4.5-fold molar excess of hydrogen. Under these conditions, no hydrogen limitation is expected, justifying the assumption of pseudo-first-order kinetics. [29] Due to the simplified isothermal consideration of the reaction kinetics, the influence of mass and heat transfer on the reaction is not taken into account.

3.2.2 Experimental Setup and Procedure

The experiment was set up largely according to Figure 1 in the kinetic laboratory of BASF SE. For confidentiality reasons, specific details about the components used are not provided.

The liquid phase was recirculated by a high-pressure gear pump and monitored via a Coriolis mass flow meter, while the hydrogen feed was controlled by a mass flow controller. The reactant mixture was preheated in a heat exchanger located directly upstream of the reactor inlet to ensure the desired reaction temperature.

Thermal control was provided by a high-temperature oil bath thermostat circulating through both the reactor's double jacket and the preheater. Given this setup and the low expected conversion (implying negligible enthalpy of reaction), the reactor reached isothermal conditions within 300 s providing well defined reaction conditions. The outlet temperature served hereby as the representative value for kinetic evaluations. Temperature and pressure sensors were therefore installed at the reactor inlet and outlet.

Downstream of the reactor, the effluent entered a phase separator (buffer tank). This vessel was agitated to ensure liquid homogeneity while facilitating off-gas separation. A diaphragm back-pressure regulator connected to the separator headspace maintained the system pressure. Excess gas and liquid were discharged via a riser pipe to the pressure control valve.

The experimental setup featured two distinct sampling ports: one located directly downstream of the reactor outlet and another at the buffer tank. The reactor outlet port allowed for monitoring the conversion per pass (differential conversion), while the buffer tank port provided samples representative of the bulk liquid composition, analogous to a hypothetical ideally mixed batch reactor. Due to the high recirculation rate, concentration gradients between the buffer tank and the reactor inlet were assumed to be negligible, so that the composition at the reactor inlet was taken to be identical to that in the buffer tank at given times.

While this peripheral setup remained constant throughout the study, the two different design options of the reactor as discussed above were integrated into the loop:

First, the thin/long reactor consisted of a 8x1 mm Hastelloy pipe with a total length of 1 m and a segment of 810 mm encased within the heating jacket. A section of the pipe was filled with an active catalyst material, while the upstream and downstream voids were filled with inert glass beads.

Second, the wide/short reactor consisted of a tubular inlay that was inserted in an existing pressure vessel resulting in geometry comparable to Figure 5. The inlay had an inner diameter of 40 mm and a length of 74 mm. As detailed in Section 2.2, this reactor was filled with the same mass of active material as the thin reactor, resulting in a catalyst layer height of 15 mm, again sandwiched between layers consisting of inert glass beads.

Prior to the kinetic batch experiments, the catalyst was conditioned in continuous operation mode for 500 h for both reactor designs. Throughout this period, fresh liquid reactant and hydrogen was continuously fed into the circuit, while the buffer tank was maintained at a constant liquid level. Due to the high recirculation rate, the system kinetically resembled a CSTR during this phase. This conditioning was continued until the concentration at the setup's outlet reached a steady state. This procedure was essential to bypass the initial phase of rapid catalyst deactivation. Since this phenomenon is a known characteristic of the catalyst employed, this pre-treatment ensured that the subsequent kinetic measurements were performed on a stabilized catalyst surface, thereby decoupling deactivation effects from the reaction kinetics. A particular strength of the reactor concept is that continuous conditioning and batch kinetic measurements can be performed in the same setup by simply switching the mode of operation.

The kinetic studies in the DRR were performed in batch-mode after filling the apparatus via a high pressure pump with reactant. The initial reaction mass targeted for each experimental run was 100 g (Section 2.3). Across the batch experiments with the two different reactor designs, the following operating conditions were varied: temperature, liquid circulation rate, and gas flow rate.

Sampling was performed manually via needle valves. To ensure representative sampling and eliminate dead-volume effects, the sampling lines were flushed prior to collecting the

actual aliquot. This pre-flush volume was discarded. Both the flush and sample masses were recorded to dynamically correct the catalyst-to-liquid ratio in the data evaluation as shown in Equation (4).

The timestamp for kinetic analysis was defined as the moment of valve closure with t_0 corresponding to the first sample, which marks the start of the kinetic evaluation.

The composition of the liquid phase was determined with UV-Vis spectroscopy using a PerkinElmer Lambda 1050+ spectrometer at a wavelength of 250–400 nm. For this analysis, the sample was diluted in methanol and measured against air in a 2 mm quartz glass cuvette in accordance with an internal analytical protocol.

4 Results

4.1 Operating Maps for DRR

Figure 9 shows the results of the simulation study comparing the transient conversion profiles of a long and thin reactor ($\delta=0.03 \text{ m m}^{-1}$) and a wide and short reactor ($\delta=0.3 \text{ m m}^{-1}$) under identical conditions.

Figure 9: Comparison of the transient conversion of a simulated exemplary DRR experiment conducted with (a) a long and thin reactor ($\delta=0.03 \text{ m m}^{-1}$) and (b) a wide and short packed bed reactor ($\delta=0.3 \text{ m m}^{-1}$) with all other parameters being identical. Ideally mixed batch reactor model (solid red line), compartment-base model for FBR inlet (dotted line) and FBR outlet (dashed line), conversion per single pass (shaded area).

Under the given conditions, the long and thin reactor exhibits a significant deviation from ideally mixed batch behavior and a significant conversion of the catalyst bed can be observed in the early stage of operation (see Figure 9a). In contrast, the wide and short reactor achieves a much closer approximation to ideally mixed batch performance, with a significantly reduced conversion over the bed (see Figure 9b). To assess the impact of the deviation from ideally mixed batch behavior on the estimated kinetic parameter, the similarity factor was calculated as described in Section 3.1.3 as a function of the diameter-to-length ratio and the superficial liquid velocities in the reactor, see Figure 10.

Figure 10: DRR performance number κ as a function of superficial fluid velocity u and reactor geometry δ calculated for a rate constant of $k = 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a split factor of $\gamma = 1$.

As expected, the similarity factor κ increases with increasing diameter-to-length ratio δ and increasing superficial liquid velocity u . However, even for the long and thin reactor, a similarity of $\kappa \geq 0.90$ can be achieved for superficial velocities as low as $u = 30 \text{ m h}^{-1}$. Thus, for typical operating conditions of the DRR, the simplified batch evaluation can yield kinetic parameters with sufficient accuracy for industrial applications, even for the long and thin reactor design.

The dependencies of the similarity factor on the diameter-to-length ratio and the superficial liquid velocities is also influenced by the reaction rate constant, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: DRR performance number κ as a function of reaction rate constant k and reactor geometry δ simulated at a superficial velocity of $u = 30 \text{ m h}^{-1}$ and a split factor of $\gamma = 1$.

As expected for fast reactions, i.e. larger reaction rate constants, the similarity factor κ decreases, indicating a greater deviation from ideally mixed batch behavior. This deviation can be mitigated by decreasing the amount of catalyst in the bed. However, this reduction could result in the sample of catalyst particles becoming too small to be representative (see also Requirement (I)).

Figure 12 shows the results of the sensitivity analysis that investigates the influence of radial maldistribution in the catalyst bed on the similarity factor κ .

Figure 12: DRR performance number κ as a function of gross fluid superficial velocity \tilde{u} and the radial fluid maldistribution ratio γ calculated for a rate constant of $k = 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\delta = 0.04$.

As described in Section 3.1.2 a bed with even radial distribution of volume flow rate has a split factor of 1. As expected, the similarity factor κ decreases with increasing maldistribution, indicating a greater deviation from ideally mixed batch behavior. However, even for a significant maldistribution with a split factor of $\gamma = 9$, a similarity factor does not deteriorate significantly from the ideal case of $\gamma = 1$. Our CFD simulation as well as studies reported in the literature indicates that a maximum maldistribution of $\gamma < 2$ can be expected when the bed has been carefully packed and the right reactor-to-particle diameter ratio was chosen (see Section 2.2). [64] Thus, we expect that the influence of radial maldistribution on the similarity factor κ is negligible for the DRR design proposed in this work. This study shows that the DRR can be describe using a ideally mixed batch reactor model for a wide range of reaction rate constants, diameter-to-length ratios, and superficial liquid velocities without significant loss of accuracy in the estimated kinetic parameters. For extreme conditions, such as very fast reactions or very long and thin reactors, the DRR can still be used for investigating the kinetics, but the more complex compartment model should be applied for data evaluation to account for the non-ideal

behavior.

In summary, the operation maps presented allow the identification of favorable design and operating regimes for a simplified evaluation based on batch kinetics:

- High ratio d/l
- High superficial fluid velocity
- Slow reaction

4.2 Experimental Kinetic Studies

Following the theoretical validation, the experimental performance of the two reactor geometries was characterized using the hydrogenation case study. For reasons of confidentiality, the experimental time, superficial velocity and temperature are given as normalized quantities \bar{t} , \bar{u} and \bar{T} . First, the validity of the fundamental design criterion, the differential conversion per pass, was verified experimentally. Figure 13 illustrates a comparison of the temporal evolution of the conversion of the aromatic species X_A measured at the inlet and the outlet of the FBR for a representative batch run in the thin/long reactor setup. In addition, the differential conversion per pass ΔX is shown, which is calculated as the difference between the inlet and outlet conversion. Furthermore, the ideally mixed batch model fit is shown, which is used to determine the reaction rate constant k for this experiment.

Figure 13: Conversion X and differential conversion ΔX in a thin/long reactor setup plotted with respect to the reaction time \bar{t} . Symbols: experimental data. Dashed line: guidance for the eye. Solid line: Batch model fit.

As established in Section 3.1.3, the applicability of the simplified batch evaluation relies on the system approaching differential conditions. In the experiment shown, the maximum differential conversion was limited to 5.5 %. As the reaction progresses and the reactant concentration decreases, ΔX declines further. This low single-pass conversion serves as a direct indicator of the DRR's ideality. Consequently, the reactor operates well within the valid design space derived in Section 4.1, justifying the use of the simple batch model (solid line in Figure 13) to describe the experimental data. The similarity factor was $\kappa = 0.976$.

To exclude external mass transfer limitations and verify the predictions from the operating maps (Figure 10), the superficial fluid velocity \bar{u} was varied between experimental runs while keeping the reaction temperature constant. Figure 14 shows the transient conversion for the thin/long reactor.

Figure 14: Transient conversion of reactant in the DRR hydrogenation reactor with the thin/long packed bed reactor. Identical temperature in all experimental runs, fluid phase superficial velocity \bar{u} varied between experimental runs. Lines are a guidance for the eye.

A distinct dependency is observed where increasing the superficial velocity initially accelerates the observed reaction rate. This trend aligns with the theoretical prediction that higher velocities reduce single-pass conversion, thereby bringing the system closer to the ideal differential state, which results in a higher apparent rate. The data indicates a maximum reaction rate plateauing at $\bar{u} = 50$. Similarly, Figure 15 depicts the results for the wide/short reactor under identical conditions.

Figure 15: Transient conversion of reactant in the DRR hydrogenation reactor with the wide/short packed bed reactor. Identical temperature in all experimental runs, fluid phase superficial velocity \bar{u} varied between experimental runs. Lines are a guidance for the eye.

Even in this geometry, higher superficial velocities lead to faster reaction progress. Crucially, this effect is consistent with the reactor model's approach to ideality rather than the elimination of mass transfer limitations. The assumption that the reaction acceleration is driven by mass transfer enhancement is contradicted by the observation of a maximum rate plateau. Furthermore, the kinetic analysis confirmed a clear first-order reaction regime, indicating that external mass transport limitations were negligible. The minor deviations observed between high-velocity runs are attributed to slight fluctuations in catalyst activity rather than hydrodynamic effects. The uncertainty in conversion was estimated to be 3 %. Therefore, the observed differences between the conversion curves of experiments conducted at $\bar{u} = 30$ and $\bar{u} = 50$ with both reactor designs exceed the measurement uncertainty and may be regarded as significant.

Finally, the temperature dependence of the reaction rate constant was examined to compare the evaluation quality of both reactor designs. Experiments were conducted at the same superficial velocity ($\bar{u} = 80$) and three distinct normalized temperatures \bar{T} with $\bar{T}_1 > \bar{T}_2 > \bar{T}_3$. Figure 16 displays the temperature dependent conversion profiles for the thin/long reactor.

Figure 16: Transient conversion of reactant in the DRR hydrogenation reactor with the thin/long packed bed reactor for three temperatures. Fluid phase superficial velocity ($\bar{u} = 80$) was the same in all experimental runs. Temperature \bar{T} varied between experimental runs ($\bar{T}_1 > \bar{T}_2 > \bar{T}_3$). Dots show experimental data. Dashed line is a guidance for the eye.

Based on these data, the Arrhenius parameters were determined using Equation (13). To assess the model accuracy, the rate constants \bar{k} were derived using both the simplified batch model and the compartment model. The results are compared in Figure 17 for the thin/long reactor and Figure 18 for the wide/short reactor.

Figure 17: Normalized reaction rate constant \bar{k} as a function of normalized temperature \bar{T} determined using the DRR setup with a thin/long reactor. Values obtained from laboratory tests are shown as dots. Solid lines represent model data obtained by using the simplified batch model and the complex compartment model.

As predicted by the operating maps shown in the previous section, deviations occur between the simple batch model and the compartment model when using the thin/long reactor configuration. The non-ideal differential conversion of the long bed introduces a small systematic error when using the simplified evaluation. In contrast, Figure 18 demonstrates that, for the wide/short reactor, both models yield consistent results.

Figure 18: Normalized reaction rate constant \bar{k} as a function of normalized temperature \bar{T} determined using the DRR setup with a wide/thin reactor. Values obtained from laboratory tests are shown as dots. Solid lines represent model data obtained by using the simplified batch model and the complex compartment model.

Crucially, the experimentally determined rate constants for the wide/short configuration align perfectly with the exponential Arrhenius fit derived from the batch model. More broadly, the distinct and smooth temperature dependence observed in both reactor geometries demonstrates high experimental consistency. This result confirms that the developed DRR setup is generally capable of generating reliable kinetic data under industrially relevant conditions.

While the rigorous compartment model can correct for the deviations in the thin reactor, its implementation requires significantly higher computational effort. The wide/short design allows for direct, accurate evaluation using the simple batch model without complex numerical fitting. However, it must be noted that for the specific reaction system considered here, the absolute differences in the determined rate constants between the two designs were minor. In the context of industrial process development, experimental uncertainties such as sampling timing or catalyst deactivation were found to be the predominant sources of error. Therefore, despite the theoretical superiority and near-ideal behavior of the wide/short design, the thin/long configuration remains a practically viable and cost-efficient alternative for this application.

5 Conclusion

This study systematically investigated the behavior of the differential recycle reactor (DRR) using sensitivity analyses and model-based evaluations. It was confirmed that the DRR increasingly approximates the behavior of an ideally mixed batch reactor as the differential conversion per pass is reduced. Concrete design criteria were quantified through the introduction of the similarity factor κ . Under suitable operating conditions, particularly at low conversions, high superficial velocities, and favorable reactor geometries, the kinetics of a first-order reaction can be determined with high accuracy using a simplified batch-model evaluation.

The simulation-based parameter studies provided a robust foundation for selecting appropriate operating conditions for the experimental DRR setup. These predictions were validated through laboratory experiments deploying an industrially relevant hydrogenation system. The experimental studies were largely consistent with the predicted behavior. The rigorous compartment model was able to comprehensively represent the observed reactor dynamics and proved to be a reliable tool for supporting kinetic analysis and reactor design. Simultaneously, the simple batch model proved entirely sufficient for routine kinetic measurements in the identified operating ranges. The observed agreement between simulation and experiment confirms the applicability of the modeling approach and supports the relevance of the proposed operating regimes for industrial applications.

Further analyses revealed that increasing the recycle rate or optimizing reactor geometry significantly improves kinetic accuracy. However, for practical implementation, degrees of freedom are limited by the resulting packing porosity, which must be carefully considered during reactor design.

Regarding the reactor configuration, a clear trade-off was identified. Two practical reactor geometries yielding the same catalyst bed porosity were evaluated: a wide/short packed bed and a thin/long packed bed. The wide/short geometry behaves analogously to an ideally mixed batch stirred tank, eliminating the need for catalyst size classification (e.g., crushing pellets) due to its favorable diameter ratio. However, this benefit is accompanied by increased constructional complexity and fluid distribution challenges.

By contrast, the thin/long reactor concept entails slight systematic deviations from ideality. Experimental results demonstrated that these theoretical deviations are minor com-

pared to other experimental uncertainties, such as sampling timing or catalyst deactivation. Consequently, due to its significant advantages in terms of engineering simplicity and operational economy, the thin/long geometry remains a practical, scalable, and robust solution for this type of investigation.

Given the DRR's verified capability to generate highly consistent and time-resolved kinetic data, the system is well suited for future coupling with online analytical instrumentation. Future studies will focus on enabling real-time kinetic investigations, with the goal of establishing the DRR as an accessible and efficient platform for obtaining high-quality reaction data in multiphase heterogeneous catalysis.

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Graphical Abstract

Combining fixed bed fluid dynamics...

